

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Anhelina Hrytsei (2025): Verified Russian Double-Tap Strikes in Ukraine (24 February 2022 – 31 August 2024) (published on Truth Hounds), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/0962F857-E63E-4938-B5E7-37E7DC66EDEB>

Abstract

The Truth Hounds' dataset of Verified Russian Double-Tap Strikes, published as part of the report "Cruelty Cascade: Examining the Pattern of Russian Double-Tap Strikes in Ukraine," includes data on 36 incidents of such attacks carried out by the Russian army between the beginning of the full-scale invasion on 24 February 2022 and 31 August 2024. The dataset, available in both Ukrainian and English, provides the locations of the attacks, descriptions of their circumstances, the approximate number of casualties, and the weapons likely used in the second strike.

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Verified Russian Double-Tap Strikes in Ukraine (24 February 2022 – 31 August 2024)

Methodological Foundation

Double-tap strikes are defined as the tactic of carrying out two or more consecutive strikes on the same target or area, with intervals between strikes of at least five minutes and up to several hours (depending on the context of the attack), which are sufficient to allow first responders to arrive and begin their activities.

Verification of double-tap strikes was conducted based on:

1. The identification of the precise locations of both attacks;
2. Confirmation that the interval between them was at least five minutes and could extend to several hours;
3. Evidence of the arrival of emergency services.

The researchers relied on online monitoring, open-source intelligence (OSINT), and fieldwork in Kharkiv, Cherkaska Lozova, Pokrovsk, Zaporizhzhia, Odesa, and Khmelnytskyi. During fieldwork each interviewee — a witness or survivor of such an attack — signed an informed consent form, and their names were anonymized for safety.

Limitations

Considering the limited availability of data, a common constraint in active armed conflict settings, the actual number of double-tap strikes that occurred between 24 February 2022 and 31 August 2024 is likely considerably higher than the number verified by the researchers. Even within the report, over 60 incidents exhibited characteristics consistent with double-tap strikes; however, based on the verification standards applied, only 36 were included in the final dataset.

Additionally, the researchers were unable to conclusively verify the casualty figures and types of weapons used in the follow-up strikes for each incident. Consequently, this information should be considered with appropriate caution.

Usage

The dataset was published as an [annex](#) to the [report](#), which offers a comprehensive analysis of double-tap strikes as a military phenomenon, examines their underlying logic, and provides an in-depth case study of attacks in the settlements of Cherkaska

Lozova (Kharkiv oblast) and Pokrovsk (Donetsk oblast). It lists 36 verified incidents of double-tap strikes, categorized across four variables:

- **Date:** day–month–year (e.g. 24 March 2024);
- **Circumstances:** a concise description of the incident, typically indicating the time interval between the attacks, the buildings damaged or destroyed, the number of casualties, and any evidence of potential legitimate military targets at the site;
- **Approximate number of casualties:** the number of individuals killed or injured as a result of the attack;
- **Likely weapon used in the follow-up strike:** the most accurate available estimate of the weapon type employed in the second strike.

The dataset covers eight oblasts (administrative divisions) of the country, where the double-tap strikes were recorded, in particular:

- **Kharkiv oblast:** 11 incidents;
- **Kherson oblast:** 9 incidents;
- **Donetsk oblast:** 4 incidents;
- **Zaporizhzhia oblast:** 4 incidents;
- **Dnipropetrovsk oblast:** 3 incidents;
- **Odesa oblast:** 3 incidents;
- **Vinnytsia oblast:** 1 incident;
- **Khmelnyskyi oblasti:** 1 incident.

The distribution by year is as follows:

- **2022:** 6 incidents;
- **2023:** 10 incidents;
- **2024:** 20 incidents.

In addition, the dataset records the types of weapons likely used in the follow-up strikes, which can be grouped into four broad categories:

- **Cruise and ballistic missiles:** 3M54-1; 9M727/9M728/9M729; 9M723;
- **Surface-to-air missiles:** 5V55; 48N6;
- **Artillery:** rocket artillery; barrel artillery;
- **Drones:** Shahed 131/136; unspecified FPV drones;
- **Other:** unspecified drone-dropped munitions.

The dataset is the only one of its kind in the context of the Russo-Ukrainian war, which makes it a valuable source of both quantitative and qualitative information on the phenomenon. At the same time, similar datasets have been compiled in other armed conflicts, which gives it important comparative value. For example, in July

2022 the Syria Justice and Accountability Center published *When the Planes Return: Double-Tap Strikes on Civilians in Syria*, which includes a comparable dataset covering double-tap strikes recorded between 2014 and 2021.¹ Notably, it contains some variables that are the same as in the TH dataset, including the dates of the attacks, their locations (settlement and governorate), and the presumed weapon used in the second strike.

As of November 2025, the TH dataset was cited in two academic pieces:

- Adriana Petryna, “The Other Humanitarians: Emergency First Responders and the Problem of Eradication-Level Harm,” *Health and Human Rights* (FXB Center for Health and Human Rights at Harvard University, March 11, 2025), <https://www.hhrjournal.org/2025/03/11/the-other-humanitarians-emergency-first-responders-and-the-problem-of-eradication-level-harm/>.
- Michael A Newton, “Russia’s Way of Total War: War Crimes and Crimes against Humanity Committed through Targeting Humanitarian Personnel and Facilities and Intentional Deprivation of Medical Care,” SSRN (Nashville: Vanderbilt Law School, August 21, 2025), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5440195.

Funding

The report was produced with the financial assistance of the European Union and National Endowment for Democracy (NED).

Note

This data review was produced by Anhelina Hrytsei, a Truth Hounds Researcher, as part of an Erasmus Traineeship at the Research Center for East European Studies at the University of Bremen.

¹ Syria Justice and Accountability Centre, “When the Planes Return: Double-Tap Strikes on Civilians in Syria,” Syria Justice and Accountability Centre (Washington, D.C.: Syria Justice and Accountability Centre, July 2022), <https://syriaaccountability.org/content/files/2022/08/English-Double-Tap-1.pdf>.